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Educational Awareness Through Visual Communication to Combat Distracted Driving in New Jersey

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Background

“Anything that takes the drivers attention away from the task of safe driving is distracted driving” (NHTSA, 2014)

There are 3 main types of distracted driving (Regan, 2008)

Visual distraction takes eye off the road

Texting
Checking GPS

Manual distraction takes hand off driving

Eating or drinking
Reaching for objects in the car

Cognitive distraction takes mind off driving

Daydreaming
Talking to passengers

COMMON TASKS AS DISTRACTIONS

- Texting/Browsing
- Receiving phone calls
- Eating/Drinking
- Smoking
- Grooming/Fidgeting
- Turning Radio/GPS
- Reaching Objects
- Talking to Passenger
- Daydreaming
- Drowsy

Background

- Distracted driving is among the top 5 causes of death in motor vehicle crashes in the USA (NHTSA, 2020)
- 3,522 fatalities and 362,415 injuries due to motor vehicle crashes involving distracted drivers in 2021 (NHTSA, 2023)
- Distracted driving is the leading cause of death in New Jersey (Rosenblum, 2021).
- 25% of the fatal motor vehicle crashes in the state of New Jersey is associated with distraction (Zutobi, 2022).

Background (Safety Countermeasures: 3E's)

Engineering & Technology

- Improve lighting
- Wide and bright striping
- In-vehicle Tracking System
- In-vehicle Alert System

Education & Awareness

- Behavioral Training
- Social Media
- Print Media
- Posters/Flyers
- Awareness Campaign

❖ Enforcement of Law

- Texting ban (20 states) and handheld cellphone ban (48 states)
- U Drive U Text U Pay campaign
- New Jersey laws fine \$200 for first offense and \$400 for second offense

Objectives

- To analyze the impact of dynamic message signs (DMS) as a visual communication on distracted driving events in the selected high crash corridors in the state of New Jersey.

Data Collection (Approach & Equipment)

- **Technique:** Moving observation vehicle running continuously through middle lane of designated corridors
- **Vehicle:** Ford (F-150) Truck
- **Data Collector:** Trained data collector on front passenger seat of observation vehicle archiving passing drivers behavior manually
- **Counter App:** Records driver behavior and archive the time
- **GPS Tracker:** Records the time and location (latitude-longitude)
- **Go-Pro Hero Camera:** Records the behavior of drivers

Figure: (a) GPS Tracker and Counter App (b) Test Vehicle on Road

Data Collection (Time & Scenario Selection)

- 7 Study locations with DMS: US-1, NJ-18, US-9, US-22, US-130, NJ-35, NJ-70 (1 weekday, 1 weekend each)
- Comparison of behavior on segments: Before (0.2 miles), during (0.1 miles), and after (0.2 miles) of the DMS
- Month of Data Collection: April 2023
- Time of Data Collection: 7 AM- 6 PM

Data Collection (Corridor Maps)

US-1 & NJ- 18

US-130

US-22

Data Collection (Corridor Maps)

US-9

NJ-35 and NJ-70

Data Integration

Data Collection (Definition of Distractions)

- **Handheld Cell Phone:** The driver is holding or using a cell phone with his/her hands.
- **Receiving Calls:** A cell phone is held near the driver's ear.
- **Eating/Drinking:** The driver's hand is occupied by a cup, food, or a cigarette, or the driver is seen eating or drinking.
- **Radio/Reaching Object:** Their hands reach toward the radio or some other place on the dash.
- **Fidgeting/Grooming:** Their hands touch their face, head, or hair.
- **Drowsy:** The driver is yawning.
- **Talking to Passenger:** Their eye or face orientation is directed toward the passenger side.
- **Non-distracted:** Their hands are on the steering wheel, and their eyes are on the road.

Data Collection Technique (Floating Car Method)

Summary of Collected Data

Period	Phone on Hand	Phone on Ear	Total Samples	Cellphone involved Distraction Rate (%)
Before Passing DMS (Freq.)	4	0	45	-
Before Passing DMS, Rate (%)	8.9	0	100.0	8.9
During Passing DMS (Freq.)	2	0	37	-
During Passing DMS, Rate (%)	5.4	0	100.0	5.4
After Passing DMS (Freq.)	1	0	75	-
After Passing DMS, Rate (%)	1.3	0	100.0	1.3
Total (Freq.)	7	0	157	-
Total rate (%)	4.5	0	100.0	4.5

Summary of Collected Data

Period	Radio/Reaching Object	Talking to Passenger	Drowsy	Food Intake	Grooming	Total Samples	Rate of Distractions not Involving Cellphone (%)
Before Passing DMS (Freq.)	1	1	1	2	5	45	-
Before Passing DMS, Rate (%)	2.2	2.2	2.2	4.4	11.1	100.0	22.1
During Passing DMS (Freq.)	1	0	2	0	2	37	-
During Passing DMS, Rate (%)	2.7	0	5.4	0	5.4	100.0	13.5
After Passing DMS (Freq.)	0	2	1	2	4	75	-
After Passing DMS, Rate (%)	0	2.7	1.3	2.7	5.3	100.0	12.0
Total (Freq.)	2	3	4	4	11	157	-
Total rate (%)	1.3	1.9	2.5	2.5	7.0	100.0	15.2

Summary of Collected Data

- Distraction rate decreased from 30.1% before DMS to 18.9% during passing DMS, and 13.3% after passing the DMS
- Rate of “Phone at hand” decreased from 8.9% before DMS to 5.4% during passing DMS, and 4.5% after passing the DMS
- The behavior of “eating/drinking”, “radio/reaching object” and “grooming” was decreased after passing the DMS compared to before passing the DMS

Event Data Analysis (Significance Test)

Type of Distraction	Mean Rank Values			Direction of Significance (↑ for increase, ↓ for decrease)		
	Position to DMS					
	Before	During	After	Before vs. During	Before vs. After	During vs. After
Phone on Hand	26.00	22.71	22.17	-	-	-
Phone on Ear	23.50	23.50	23.50	-	-	-
Radio/Reaching Object	24.11	24.18	22.50	-	-	-
Talking to Passenger	23.71	22.00	24.50	-	-	-
Drowsy	23.14	24.89	22.69	-	-	-
Food Intake	24.86	21.50	24.00	-	-	-
Grooming	27.04	21.71	22.14	-	-	-
Non-Distracted	16.71	25.11	27.53	↑	↑	-

Conclusions

- Non-distracted driving significantly increased during and after the drivers passed the DMS signs, compared to before passing the DMS sign.
- Frequency of phone on hand also decreased after drivers passed the DMS, compared to before or during passing the DMS location
- Road sections with DMS sign displaying "U Drive-U Text-U Pay" was found to be signalized during April 2023
- Educational messages like "U Drive-U Text-U Pay" or "One text or call, can wreck it all" help mitigate distraction.
- This study's findings demonstrate that an effective educational awareness campaign through visual communication can help reduce this risky driving behavior

Limitations

- Data were collected through specific times of the day (7 AM- 6 PM). No nighttime data was included in this study.
- The total sample size in this study was low due to the lack of information on DMS locations and their associated messages
- The number of DMS locations for this study are limited to 7 and those locations are on the selected high crash corridors/highways (interstate and arterial roads) only. The effect of DMS on local roads could not be gathered from this study as local roads were outside the scope of the study.
- None of the overhead DMS were functioning in the study routes during the data collection period in April 2023. Hence, this study findings are only indicative of the DMS signs on the side of the roads.

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Thank You